

Mission Planning and Weather Sensing for Autonomous Surface Vehicles

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Abstract. Effective mission planning for autonomous vessels requires balancing safety, efficiency, and waypoint priority in dynamic marine environments. This paper presents a framework for optimal mission planning that combines environmental modeling, simulation, optimization, and machine learning. The system incorporates wave and wind forecasts, including machine-learning local forecasts, into a mission simulator. Extending the general orienteering approach, a genetic algorithm is employed to identify vessel routes that maximize priority scores, adhere to fuel constraints, avoid hazardous conditions, and meet waypoint arrival times. Results show that the optimizer consistently generates high-quality missions, and the predictive weather model provides sufficient short-term accuracy to guide vessels along safe and efficient paths with minimal need for replanning.

Key words: USV, Mission replanning Machine learning, Seakeeping, Fuel consumption

1. Introduction

Autonomous vessels, such as uncrewed surface vessels (USVs) are increasingly used for environmental monitoring, logistics, defense, and research. However, planning efficient and safe missions in dynamic marine conditions remains a significant challenge. Ocean environments are unpredictable, with constantly changing wave and wind conditions that can threaten mission success or vessel safety. Mission planners must balance fuel constraints, arrival windows, and priority scores at various waypoints while navigating this uncertainty. Additionally, weather forecasts are uncertain and may not be available to USVs during missions. Traditional static planning methods are often inadequate in such dynamic contexts. The problem is further complicated by the sheer number of possible mission paths, as evaluating every potential route becomes computationally infeasible, especially as the number of waypoints increases. This paper proposes an efficient mission planning and re-planning approach based on extending the generalized orienteering problem with machine learning weather forecasts and a custom genetic algorithm. This approach is evaluated on a series of missions using actual weather hindcast data, and is shown to be an efficient option for USV mission planning.

Certain aspects of USV mission planning have been widely explored in the literature. Chu et al. [1] provide a recent review of what we term *local* path-finding algorithms - those concerned about navigating to exact waypoints and avoiding generic obstacles. Gall [2] and Yu [10] provide recent examples of such approaches. At the other extreme, several recent publications have addressed coordinating fleets of USVs, and even USVs combined with air-based vehicles for efficient search [7, 6, 11]. However, relatively few papers have explored marine-specific considerations, including realistic fuel consumption, weather and motions forecast, along with the ability to re-plan missions during their execution. Page et al. [9] considered at-sea resupply for fuel with a maritime digital twin for a fleet of USVs, while Guo et al. [4] demonstrated a bi-level algorithm considering cargo movement at a top level and path control at a lower level. The integration of marine-specific constraints, especially uncertain weather reflected through vessel motions, remains a relatively under-explored area. This is especially true for defense applications, where access to off-vessel weather forecasts and planning assistance may not be guaranteed.

This paper presents an integrated framework that combines environmental prediction and optimal mission planning. We develop a simulation-based planning system that uses a genetic algorithm to generate

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fuel-constrained, priority-maximizing routes and applies a neural network to predict wave characteristics for future planning. This combination allows vessels to execute near-optimal missions that are both safe and efficient in uncertain conditions. The following sections detail how the simulation, optimization, and prediction components interact. We also evaluate the system’s performance on an example mission to assess solution quality and the predictive model’s impact on mission planning.

2. Methodology

2.1. Problem Formulation

The problem of mission planning for a USV is formulated as a version of the orienteering problem [3], which itself is a combination of the travelling salesman problem and the knapsack problem. In this formulation, the USV must select both the number and order of potential waypoints to visit, out of a vector of all possible potential waypoints, \mathbf{WP} , while complying with seakeeping, time, and fuel burn limitations, expressed as a vector of inequality constraints $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$. Mathematically, the resulting problem can be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} && f(\mathbf{x}) \\ & \text{subject to} && g_i(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ & && \mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{WP}, \\ & && f(\mathbf{x}) = - \sum_{\mathbf{x}} V_{wp}(x_i, t_i) \\ & && V_{wp}(x_i) \text{ gives the value of visiting the } x_i \text{ waypoint at a specified time, } t_i \end{aligned}$$

2.2. Mission and Environment Model

To visualize and collect data, we developed a mission and environmental model. The environmental model incorporates wave and wind data corresponding to specific timestamps and geographic coordinates. Timestamps occur every six hours, beginning on January 1, 2018 at 00:00 and ending on December 31, 2018 at 18:00. This data is sourced from the EU and covers the North Atlantic Ocean during the year 2018. The mission model simulates a vessel’s journey using a vessel object and a mission object. A mission object, shown in Figure 1, consists of a list of destinations, each with a priority score, a goal arrival time, and an associated waypoint with a latitude and longitude. Figure 2 shows an example mission scenario with four vessels, each assigned its own mission.

The vessel object tracks speed, heading, and fuel weight throughout the simulation. To ensure accurate distance and heading calculations between waypoints, we utilize the Python library GeographicLib. Speed normally remains constant based on an input to each vessel object, but it can be dynamically decreased based on ocean conditions. For each segment between waypoints, the starting position and four additional positions along the path are evaluated. The hindcasts from the environmental model are used for the vessel’s current position. Predicted wave conditions from the machine learning model are utilized at each of the four points between the vessel’s position and the next waypoint (see *Section 2.6.*). If a segment is deemed unsafe, the remainder of the mission is replanned using the mission planning algorithm (see *Section 2.5.*).

2.3. Vessel motions and fuel consumption

Fuel consumption is estimated using resistance, propulsion, and engine models. The resistance model is based on the NPL round-bilge semi-displacement series, using the data presented in Molland et al. [8]. A custom radial basis function is fit to the wave resistance at each of the originally tested speeds, using the series’ geometric parameters as the feature space. Then, at each point in the mission, an updated displacement and parameters of the hullform (including the impact of burning off fuel) are determined and the current wave resistance is estimated. This is combined with an ITTC-1957 friction line approach for

Figure 1.: Example class structure of the vessel simulation.

Figure 2.: Visualization of a mission simulation with four vessels; the white vessel lies outside the figure's latitude/longitude range.

frictional resistance, with thrust deduction factors and wake fraction estimates made from Bailey's extension of the NPL data, as presented in Molland et al. The propulsion model incorporates propeller characteristics, including pitch, pitch/diameter ratio, A_e/A_o ratio, and the number of blades, using the Wageningen B-Series Propeller Regression. The engine model uses lookup tables for propeller RPM, power, and fuel consumption rates, along with a predefined gear ratio based on data from several manufacturers for high-speed marine diesel engines.

Fuel consumption is calculated using the Run Machinery function within the propulsion simulation. This function takes in the vessel's speed, current fuel weight, and operation time, then, using the steps described above, calculates the amount of fuel burned over that period.

To simulate wave-induced vessel motions, linear seakeeping is used to predict heave and pitch responses based on vessel speed, heading, and wave conditions. For small USVs, the linear theory may miss some of the geometric non-linearities in the response; however, for reasonable motion limits, these effects were judged to be small. This implements the simplified RAO expressions presented in Jensen et al. [5]. At each ocean coordinate, a Bretschneider wave spectrum is generated, and response spectra are computed using the Jensen Heave-Pitch RAO model. The RMS response is obtained by integrating the response spectrum and taking its square root. If this value exceeds a predefined threshold (e.g., 1.5), vessel speed is reduced

to mimic heavy-weather speed reduction on crewed vessels. These adjustments impact propulsion and resistance forces, resulting in more realistic estimates of speed and fuel consumption.

2.4. Exact Solution for Benchmarking Early Mission Plans

Before incorporating variables such as weather conditions and arrival-time-based priority decay, the mission planning problem could be solved exactly by evaluating all possible missions and selecting the one with the highest total priority score that satisfied the fuel constraint. This early-stage solution was essential for benchmarking and validating the performance of the genetic algorithm. To optimize this process, the algorithm first generates all possible combinations of destinations and sorts them by priority score. It then iterates through these combinations, starting with the highest priority score. For each combination, a branch-and-bound algorithm determines the most fuel-efficient route through the waypoints. If the route meets the fuel constraint, the corresponding mission is selected as optimal. Otherwise, the process continues with the next highest-priority combination until a valid mission is found.

2.5. Genetic Algorithm for Optimal Mission Planning

As the problem complexity increased with the introduction of additional variables, the exact method became infeasible. To address this, a genetic algorithm was developed to efficiently explore the solution space and approximate an optimal mission plan. This algorithm begins by initializing a population of 100 individuals. Each individual represents a mission by using a chromosome that contains indices of destinations from the destination list. Individuals also track the mission's total priority score, which depends on the sequence and timing of waypoint visits. If a vessel arrives at a waypoint too late, the associated priority score for that waypoint is reduced to reflect the delay. Constraint violations are also recorded, such as exceeding the fuel limit or entering dangerous ocean conditions.

To evolve the population toward an optimal solution, the algorithm follows these steps:

1. Selection

Two-pass tournament selection is used to build a selection pool of individuals. First, the population is randomly shuffled. Then, adjacent individuals are compared in pairs, and the better individual from each pair is added to the selection list. This process is repeated a second time to maintain the population size.

To compare individuals, the algorithm prioritizes feasibility first and performance second. If one individual violates constraints and the other does not, the feasible individual is always selected, regardless of score. If both individuals are feasible, the one with the higher total waypoint priority score is preferred. If both have constraint violations, the individual with the smaller total violation is considered better.

2. Crossover

The algorithm iterates through the selection pool, selecting pairs of individuals (parents) to produce children. For each pair:

- A random number between 0 and 1 is generated. If the number is less than 0.75, crossover occurs.
- If crossover is performed:
 - A random integer n is chosen between 1 and the length of the shorter parent chromosome.
 - **Child 1** inherits indices 0 to n from **Parent 1** and n to the end from **Parent 2**.
 - **Child 2** inherits indices 0 to n from **Parent 2** and n to the end from **Parent 1**.
 - Duplicate waypoints in each child chromosome are identified and removed.

3. Mutation

If crossover occurs, another random number between 0 and 1 is generated. If the number is less than 0.1, a mutation is applied. One of the following four mutation types is selected at random:

- **Partial Reverse** – A random segment of the chromosome is reversed (i.e., waypoints are visited in the opposite order).
- **Drop Waypoint** – A randomly selected waypoint is removed from the chromosome.
- **Add Waypoint** – A new, non-duplicate waypoint is inserted at a random position.
- **Replace Waypoint** – An existing waypoint is replaced with a new, non-duplicate waypoint.

Once the next generation is formed, the algorithm ensures the best individuals aren't discarded by checking if the two best individuals from the previous generation are present in the new population. If not, they replace the worst individuals. This process repeats for 30 generations to find the optimal mission.

2.6. Machine Learning Model to Predict Future Wave Heights, Headings, and Periods

In some cases, a USV may not have access to offboard weather forecasts. In these situations, past observations can be used to make future predictions of weather, allowing route planning to continue. To achieve this, we developed a machine learning model that predicts future wave heights, headings, and periods. The model is based on a feed-forward neural network and implemented using PyTorch. The neural network was set up with four fully connected layers. It takes 21 input features:

- Wave height at 0, 6, 12, and 18 hours prior.
- Wave heading at 0, 6, 12, and 18 hours prior.
- Wave period at 0, 6, 12, and 18 hours prior
- Wind speed at 0, 6, 12, and 18 hours prior
- Wave direction at 0, 6, 12, and 18 hours prior
- The forecast horizon — the amount of time into the future (between 1 and 72 hours) the model will predict.

The network architecture consists of layers with the following dimensions: 21–64, 64–128, 128–64, and 64–4, with the ReLU activation function applied between layers. The model outputs four predicted values: wave height, sine component of wave heading, cosine component of wave heading, and wave period.

The model used 18,000 randomly sampled data points from the 2018 EU North Atlantic Ocean dataset. Training used 70% of this data and was conducted over 800 epochs using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0005. A weighted mean squared error loss function was employed, placing greater emphasis on larger wave heights during training to improve performance on high-impact conditions. No additional weighting was applied to the heading or period outputs. The model was validated using the remaining 30% of the data.

2.7. Mission Replanning

To account for potential errors in the machine learning model's predictions, a mission replanning mechanism was incorporated into the simulation. Replanning is triggered in two scenarios:

- The vessel encounters unsafe ocean conditions between its last and next waypoint, as determined during the vessel speed adjustments based on wave-induced motions modeled by the RAO calculations (see *Section 2.3*). If unsafe conditions are detected, the corresponding timestamp is added to a time blacklist for the upcoming waypoint. This instructs the genetic algorithm to avoid selecting that waypoint within a six-hour window before or after the flagged time.
- The vessel arrives at a waypoint more than 10 hours later than the estimated arrival time calculated during the initial GA planning.

In either case, the GA is reinitialized and replans the mission for the remaining unvisited waypoints, using the current timestamp and the most recently visited waypoint as the new starting point.

3. Results

3.1. Machine Learning Model Performance

Building upon the methods outlined in the previous section, we now present the results of the USV mission planning framework. First, the weather prediction machine learning model is isolated to evaluate its predictive performance. Next, an example mission scenario is examined to evaluate the effectiveness of the genetic algorithm and the mission replanning strategy. This analysis also assesses the machine learning model's performance under realistic conditions.

Figures 3–5 present the model's predictive performance on the validation dataset. For each prediction category, two types of visualizations are provided: a scatter plot and a histogram. The scatter plots display the relationship between the predicted and actual values, with the ideal prediction line represented by $x = y$ (i.e., predicted = actual). The color of each data point indicates the forecast horizon, illustrating how prediction accuracy varies with the time interval into the future. A polar plot is used in place of a linear scatter plot for wave heading predictions. In this visualization, points closer to the center represent more accurate predictions. The accompanying histograms overlay the distributions of predicted and actual values, enabling a direct comparison of how well the model captures the true distribution for each variable.

Figure 3.: Scatter Plot(a) and Histogram(b) of predicted vs. actual wave heights.

Figure 4.: Polar Plot(a) and Histogram(b) of predicted vs. actual wave headings.

Figure 5.: Scatter Plot(a) and Histogram(b) of predicted vs. actual wave periods.

3.2. Mission Planning Algorithm

The following tables and figures present the setup and results of a mission simulation for a vessel. The vessel departs from and returns to the coordinates 49.1° , -35° , starting at 07:00 UTC on March 1, 2018. It begins the mission with 100 kilonewtons of fuel and travels at a speed of 20 knots.

Table 1.: Vessel Dimensions

Length (m)	Beam (m)	Wetted Surface Area(m^2)	Draft (m)	Volume (m^3)
45.0	7.0	100.0	3.0	472.5

Table 2.: The original mission waypoints

Latitude ($^\circ$)	Longitude ($^\circ$)	Arrival Time (UTC)	Priority Score
49.0	-34.0	2018-03-15 08:00	1
50.0	-35.0	2018-03-17 17:00	7
48.0	-33.0	2018-03-05 02:00	9
49.0	-35.0	2018-03-06 03:00	4
50.0	-34.0	2018-03-02 04:00	1
50.0	-33.0	2018-03-05 05:00	7
42.0	-49.0	2018-03-02 06:00	9
46.0	-37.0	2018-03-02 10:00	80
48.0	-34.0	2018-03-08 05:00	20
48.5	-35.0	2018-03-01 05:00	29
44.0	-35.0	2018-03-07 05:00	20
42.0	-35.0	2018-03-02 05:00	2
48.0	-25.0	2018-03-09 15:00	77
49.0	-25.0	2018-03-01 15:00	100
42.0	-20.0	2018-03-05 17:00	7

Maximum Possible Priority Score: 373

Table 3.: The initial mission found by the genetic algorithm. The planned mission prioritizes waypoints with higher scores while ensuring fuel and time constraints are met.

Latitude ($^\circ$)	Longitude ($^\circ$)	Arrival Time (UTC)	Priority Score
48.5	-35.0	2018-03-01 08:48	29
46.0	-37.0	2018-03-01 17:20	80
48.0	-34.0	2018-03-02 01:56	20
49.0	-25.0	2018-03-02 20:08	100
48.0	-25.0	2018-03-02 23:08	77
48.0	-33.0	2018-03-03 15:15	9
44.0	-35.0	2018-03-04 03:57	20

Total Priority Score:335

Table 4.: The final executed mission. Differences between the planned and executed missions reflect dynamic adjustments made during simulation.

Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)	Arrival Time (UTC)	Priority Score
48.5	-35.0	2018-03-01 08:48	29
46.0	-37.0	2018-03-01 17:20	80
48.0	-34.0	2018-03-02 01:56	20
49.0	-25.0	2018-03-02 20:08	100
48.0	-25.0	2018-03-02 23:08	77
44.0	-35.0	2018-03-04 08:58	20
48.0	-33.0	2018-03-04 21:41	9
50.0	-33.0	2018-03-05 03:41	7
49.0	-35.0	2018-03-05 08:37	4
Total Priority Score:			346

After executing the mission, the vessel arrived back at the start, 49.1°, -35°, at 08:55 UTC on March 5th, 2018. The vessel ended with 16.38 kilonewtons of fuel remaining.

To further evaluate the performance of the genetic algorithm, the same mission planning scenario used above was executed 20 times using different random seeds. Each run used the same configuration: 100 individuals over 30 generations. The final priority score achieved in each run was recorded and used to compute the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum scores. The results are as follows:

Table 5.: Distribution of final priority scores from 20 runs of the genetic algorithm with different random seeds.

Metric	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Priority Score	325.75	16.34	298	347

Figure 6 presents the results of applying the genetic algorithm-based mission planner to the scenario outlined in Table 2.. Each subplot tracks the algorithm’s performance across generations using three metrics: the best score, the mean score, and the mean score of individuals with no constraint violations. The best score represents the highest-achieving mission plan that satisfies all fuel and time constraints. The mean score indicates the average priority score of the entire population in a given generation, while the mean score no violation reflects the average score of only those solutions that meet all mission constraints. Each metric is expressed as a proportion of the maximum possible priority score, representing the total priority score of all unvisited destinations.

Subplots (a) and (b) show the initial mission plan and the replan, respectively. Each run used a population size of 100 over 30 generations, evaluating a total of 3,000 individuals per run. The algorithm considered all 15 waypoints for the initial plan, resulting in approximately 3.3 trillion possible routes. In the replan, after the vessel had visited 5 waypoints, the search space was reduced to 10 remaining destinations and about 986 thousand possible routes.

(a) Genetic algorithm performance of the initially planned mission. (b) Genetic algorithm performance of the mission replan.

Figure 6.: Genetic algorithm performance for the initial mission plan and replan.

4. Discussion

4.1. Machine Learning Model Performance

The model performs well at predicting wave height but struggles with certain wave headings and periods, as shown in Figures 3–5. In Figure 3, the scatterplot shows accurate predictions for wave heights between 0 and 8 meters, with most points closely following the best-fit line. For wave heights above 8 meters, the model tends to slightly underpredict, especially for forecasts beyond 24 hours. However, the model still correctly identifies these as higher-than-average wave conditions—it just underestimates the exact magnitude. This outcome is favorable from a safety perspective as the model does not miss the presence of large waves, which is critical for route planning. The histogram further supports this interpretation: wave heights below 2 meters and over 8 meters are underpredicted, while wave heights between 4 and 8 meters are slightly overpredicted. Heading predictions are accurate outside the range of 100–250 degrees. Within this range, performance drops, likely due to a lack of representative training data for those headings. Wave period forecasts are reliable for prediction horizons under 30 hours but degrade in accuracy beyond that point.

Evaluating the model on a sample mission further confirms its effectiveness. Using the predicted wave data in place of the actual wave data resulted in only one replan during execution. These results demonstrate that the neural network produced sufficiently accurate predictions to support safe planning decisions and reduce the frequency of mission replanning. Although not perfect, the forecasts enabled the vessel to proceed through most of the mission with minimal deviation, reinforcing the effectiveness of even moderately accurate predictions in dynamic planning.

4.2. Genetic Algorithm Performance

The genetic algorithm successfully identifies a near-optimal mission plan by balancing fuel constraints, time windows, and priority scores. As shown in Table 3., the original mission visited 7 waypoints and achieved a total priority score of 335. The final executed mission, outlined in Table 4., visited 9 waypoints with a score of 346. Figure 6 offers further insight into the algorithm’s behavior. In each run, the best score improves across generations before plateauing, suggesting that the genetic algorithm converges toward a high-quality solution.

One clear trend observed in both the optimized and executed routes is the algorithm’s consistent preference for high-priority waypoints. For instance, the waypoints at (49, -25) and (48, -25), which have the highest priority scores, are selected in both missions despite being significantly farther than most other op-

tions. In contrast, another far away waypoint at (42, -20), with a much lower priority score, is excluded from both plans. Other closer waypoints, like (48,-33), are still included. This demonstrates that the genetic algorithm effectively prioritizes value while still respecting operational limits like fuel capacity and weather avoidance. Lower-priority destinations are often excluded when they significantly increase travel cost or risk without sufficient benefit.

The dynamic replanning strategy also helped to fine-tune the route as the mission progressed. Each replan had to consider a smaller number of remaining waypoints, dropping from over three trillion possible routes initially to less than one million in the replan. This reduction in search space allowed the algorithm to focus more intensively on the most promising regions of the solution space and adapt to changing conditions. This is shown in the faster convergence in Figure 6b compared to Figure 6a.

To further assess the reliability and consistency of the genetic algorithm, the same initial mission planning task was executed 20 times with different random seeds. As shown in Table 5., the algorithm achieved a mean priority score of 326 with a standard deviation of 16, and scores ranging from 298 to 347. This relatively low variance demonstrates that the algorithm consistently produces high-quality mission plans across different runs. While some variation exists, the narrow spread in scores suggests that the approach is both stable and reliable under repeated trials.

Overall, these results validate the genetic algorithm’s ability to generate and adapt mission plans that are both feasible and high-performing in complex, constrained environments.

4.3. Limitations

While the proposed framework performed well in the simulated scenario, the limitations must be acknowledged. First, the system’s effectiveness is highly dependent on the accuracy of the machine learning model. Errors in predicted wave height, heading, or period can compromise mission safety or efficiency, particularly if hazardous conditions are underestimated. Second, although the genetic algorithm offers a computationally efficient alternative to exhaustive search, it does not guarantee globally optimal solutions. In complex or large-scale mission scenarios, the algorithm may converge prematurely to suboptimal solutions, especially if the solution space contains many local optima or is poorly explored due to limited population diversity or tuning. Finally, this study evaluated a single mission scenario. Broader validation across diverse environments, weather patterns, and vessel configurations is needed to generalize the findings.

5. Conclusion

This work addresses the challenges of planning autonomous USV missions in dynamic and uncertain ocean environments. We presented an integrated approach that combines genetic algorithm-based optimization with machine learning to overcome the limitations of static planning in marine operations. A machine learning approach was able to forecast future weather conditions with sufficient accuracy for mission planning out to about 30 hours into the future. By extending the generalized orienteering problem to incorporate wave forecasts and fuel constraints, the proposed framework enables USVs to generate adaptive mission plans that balance safety, fuel efficiency, and waypoint priority. The genetic algorithm was found to be reasonably consistent and robust over sample missions and weather windows.

This work contributes to a growing body of research focused on enabling autonomous systems to operate reliably in uncertain, data-limited environments. Future work will focus on extending the genetic algorithm to include vessel speed as a decision variable, which may improve motion efficiency and reduce fuel consumption. Enhancements to the machine learning model will include incorporating more diverse wave direction data to improve heading prediction and exploring whether using vessel motion data instead of wave characteristics can yield similarly accurate predictions. Overall, our approach offers a practical and scalable solution for USV mission planning in the face of environmental uncertainty.

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